

Randomised Controlled Trials of Interventions in Acute Kidney Injury in Critical Illness: Protocol for a scoping review

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Abstract

Background

Randomised clinical trials (RCTs) in intensive care (ICU) have not delivered effective therapies or management strategies for acute kidney injury (AKI). New treatments are emerging, including repurposing currently used medications, adapting current organ support strategies, and advancing our use of renal replacement therapy. Furthermore, there is a growing application of innovative trial designs in critical care which have the potential to improve the generation of evidence of clinical effectiveness. However, the use of newer trial designs is not straightforward: selection of patient cohorts, timing and definition of AKI risk or diagnosis, choice of outcome, handling of death and missing data, and analysis strategy for these trials in AKI remains unclear.

Methods

We will conduct a scoping review in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews. We will search PubMed Medline for RCTs conducted in adult ICU patients assessing interventions for AKI from 2004 and onwards. We will summarise data on AKI subtypes, timing and inclusion criteria, outcome measures and definitions, and effect measures and statistical methods used for analysis.

Discussion

This scoping review will provide information that may guide discussions with researchers and patients to help inform planning, execution, and analysis of future RCTs of AKI interventions.

Introduction

Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) is defined by rapid rise in serum creatinine or reduction in urine output and affects over half of the patients admitted to critical care.(1) AKI represents the result of a variety of kidney specific and non-specific insults during critical illness (2) and frequently impacts on the dysfunction of other organs.(3) In addition, interventions or treatment strategies in critical illness are often related to kidney function, for example antibiotic dosing in sepsis (4), or prescription of intravenous fluids.(5) Importantly, many patients with AKI will go on to require renal replacement therapy (RRT) to manage severe metabolic or fluid disturbances and facilitate the ongoing management of underlying conditions and other organ dysfunctions. Unfortunately, there has been a lack of convincing outcome improvement at predefined statistical significance thresholds in RCTs of interventions for ICU patients with AKI.(6–8) An apparent failure of RCTs to deliver statistical significance or disappointing replication results has not been unique to trials in AKI but is present across critical care and other specialties.(9–11)

New or “innovative” trial designs for example platform trials, adaptive recruitment, and Bayesian inference have been proposed as potential solution to the current issues with RCTs.(7,8,12) Innovative designs are well established in oncology (13) and more recently have been deployed in critical care for COVID-19.(14,15) Encouragingly, as a continuation of this pipeline, a platform trial tackling the traditional critical care syndrome of ARDS has recently started recruiting.(16) With the “rise of adaptive platform trials in critical care”(17) there is a growing potential for their application in the clinical evaluation of AKI. Our knowledge of AKI has improved, with an appreciation of different stages of AKI such as the use of biomarkers to identify kidney stress enabling early interventions(18), and better understanding of potential subphenotypes of AKI and patient characteristics such as sex.(19–21) However there are several challenges to the successful application of innovative trial designs in the evaluation of AKI interventions.

AKI is a heterogeneous syndrome with a complex, multifactorial pathophysiology, and unclear trajectory in critical illness.(8,22,23) The definition of AKI remains reliant on serum creatinine changes or urine output assessment which are both insensitive and delayed

markers of kidney function limiting scope for intervention to prevent AKI. Similarly, AKI subgroups are becoming increasingly relevant such as sepsis associated AKI (24) which may benefit from specific therapies. Furthermore, the selection of appropriate patient cohorts and trial end points remains unclear, including strategies to model and analyse non-mortality or composite outcomes. (25)

In summary, the selection of appropriate patient cohorts, timing of interventions, and optimal choice of outcomes for RCTs in AKI remains unsolved. We will conduct a scoping review to summarise the current landscape of AKI RCTs trials. We aim to collate knowledge from previous and currently recruiting RCTs across the spectrum of AKI management in critical care. We will describe the inclusion criteria used and their timing around or during ICU admission alongside reporting of the range of outcomes measures. We will then use this information to propose a potential framework for a future AKI trial.

Methods

Review protocol

This protocol has been prepared in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist.(26) (see Supplement). The protocol was published prior to initiation of the scoping review. We did not receive external funding.

Context and research questions

This scoping review will be conducted with the aim of informing patient cohort selection, outcome choices, definitions, and statistical analysis plans for a future AKI trial.

We aim to answer the following research questions:

- What definitions of AKI or AKI risk are used and at what timepoint?
- What subtype/subphenotype of AKI are included in recent AKI RCTs (e.g. cardiac/sepsis associated AKI) and how are they defined?
- What patient characteristics are recorded and how are these included in analyses?

- Which patient-important outcomes are used in recent RCTs conducted in adult ICU patients and how are they defined and prioritised?
- Which assessment time points are used (e.g., in-hospital, 30-day, 90-day, 1-year, etc), and is censoring/truncation/time-to-event considered?
- Which effect measures and statistical analyses/models are used?

Search strategy and eligibility criteria

PubMed MEDLINE will be searched from May 2004 until the present day, to reduce the risk of retrieving outdated or obsolete measures used before the first publication of the consensus diagnostic criteria for AKI. We will screen the bibliography list of identified studies as well as methodology papers for additional references. Searches will also include trial registries including Clinical Trials (www.ClinicalTrials.gov) and Current Controlled Trials (<http://www.controlled-trials.com/isrctn/>). Case series/studies, retrospective study designs, quality improvement, safety, feasibility, and physiological response to intervention studies will be excluded. The full search strategy is presented in the Supplement.

We will include RCTs in adult patients (≥ 18 years of age) with AKI or whereby AKI is the primary outcome that commenced recruitment after publication of the RIFLE definition in May 2004.(27) Articles published only in abstract form or foreign language will be excluded. Only actual RCT reports will be included (including secondary publications reporting longer term outcomes and similar); additional secondary studies using data from RCTs will be excluded. We do not plan to contact study authors for additional details. The search will be updated close to finalisation of the manuscript.

AKI definition and patient selection

We will assess studies using the framework suggested by Zarbock et al. First, study type including prevention, attenuation, or treatment of AKI. Second, we will assess patient cohort selection including the three main types of enrichment methods(28): methods that decrease baseline variability, prognostic enrichment strategies (to identify patients who are more likely to develop the end point) and predictive enrichment strategies (to identify patients who are more likely to respond to the intervention). Specific AKI subgroups or subphenotypes (such as post cardiac surgery AKI) will be recorded. Inclusion criteria will be

defined as any variable used for the AKI definition by the RCT; these include consensus AKI definitions cited. All time criteria that specified inclusion into the RCT based on the duration of AKI or RRT will be extracted (time since diagnosis of AKI, time since onset of RRT, and time since admission). In RCTs, where AKI inclusion criteria are not explicitly listed, we will assume that criteria corresponded to the AKI definition cited in the body of the text or references. In addition, we will include studies reporting use of a biomarker to enrol patients. Criteria limiting RCT eligibility of patients will be treated as exclusion criteria and will be extracted from the RCTs.

Outcomes

The following groups of outcomes will be assessed:

- Mortality based outcomes at study defined timepoints.
- AKI stage, serum creatinine (or eGFR), and AKI biomarkers outcomes including: “percentage change” or “change from baseline” type outcomes that meet an AKI criteria (e.g. KDIGO)
- Kidney specific non-mortality or composite patient centred outcomes such as Major Adverse Kidney Event (MAKE), Acute Kidney Disease (AKD). chronic kidney disease (CKD) or end stage renal disease (ESRD) requiring dialysis.
- Common ICU trial non-mortality patient important outcomes such as "Days alive without..."-type outcomes, health related quality of life (HRQoL) outcomes (any tool assessing HRQoL at or after ICU discharge), functional (including physical function)/cognitive/neurological outcomes, including frailty, dependency status and location-based outcomes if reported (e.g., number of patients in nursing homes, etc) at or after ICU discharge.

These groups are partly based on the proposed framework by Zarbock et al. In addition we will assess the use of common non-mortality outcomes as defined by Granholm et al (25). We will record the use and analysis of composite outcomes due to their common adoption in AKI trials.

Data items

Data extraction will be performed independently and in duplicate. The following data will be extracted from each included RCT: digital object identifier, journal, author, trial acronym, year, countries included, number of centres, number of patients, inclusion criteria, intervention types (drug/management/device [including rrt], as previously defined (29)), interventions, full protocol available and included with/referenced in publication (yes/no); and for each outcome, the outcome, definition/tool used, outcome prioritisation ([co-]primary outcome [yes/no]), prioritisation of outcomes containing multiple components (e.g., MAKE), assessment time points including censoring/truncation/time-to-event, proportion of dead patients, operationalisation of death, missing data proportion and handling, effect measure(s) used and statistical analysis used. We will use the PROGRESS framework to report participant characteristics (30): place of residence, race, ethnicity, culture, language, occupation, gender, sex, and social capital. Data will be extracted using a standardised spreadsheet form (Supplement); the form will be pilot tested on the first 10 studies by at least 2 authors and revised as necessary before data is extracted for the remaining studies.

Data synthesis

We will summarise data using medians with interquartile ranges (IQRs) for numeric data, numbers and percentages for categorical data. We will separate data according to various categories such as: AKI subtypes, intervention types, and outcome types. No assessment of risk of bias will be performed.

Ethics and dissemination

No ethics approval is required as data is already available in the public domain. The results of this scoping review will be reported in an international peer-reviewed journal regardless of findings. If any protocol amendments or deviations are necessary, they will be described with reasonings in the final report.

Discussion

The outlined scoping review will provide important information on the patient cohort selection, definition of AKI, and choice of outcomes in contemporary RCTs of interventions

for ICU associated AKI. This overview will help inform a strategy to design new RCTs to address the current “therapeutic gap” for AKI.

Our strengths include the adherence to the current conduct and reporting guidance for scoping reviews (26) and publication of a protocol prior to commencement. There are several limitations. First, multiple ICU trials often feature AKI as a secondary outcome (31) or investigate patients with AKI as a subgroup of the main trial.(32) The treatment effect estimates from these studies will not be assessed by this scoping review and therefore we may miss potential intervention types or strategies. However, to include such work the overall scope would need to be considerably extended and such work is more prone to confounding and false discovery limiting utility to inform future RCT design.(33) Second, the use of new biomarkers for AKI is growing but there is no standardised approach or consensus guidance on individual assays limiting potential to inform future trials. Regardless, their application can be broadly assessed using the recent ADQI consensus statement.(34) Finally, there is no standard list or core outcome set for AKI trials, hence it is the authors best effort to capture outcome types. We adopted a similar approach to Granholm et al to capture non-mortality outcomes.

In conclusion, this scoping review will provide information that may guide discussions with researchers and patients to help inform planning, execution, and analysis of future RCTs of AKI interventions.

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